

An Innovative Transformerless Single-Stage Buck-Boost Inverter Designed for Single-Phase Grid-Connected Solar PV Systems

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Abstract— An inventive single-phase grid-connected solar topology was used in this study. Photovoltaic applications, namely, buck-boost transformer-less inverters, are introduced. This configuration effectively mitigates leakage currents by ensuring that if input photovoltaic sources are comparable to grid's neutral point. Additionally, the proposed design exhibits robust maximum power point tracking (MPPT) capabilities, even under substantial variations in the input PV voltage, facilitated through the buck-boost mechanism. A further advantages of this topology is the incorporation of a singular across the two half-cycles of the grid, thereby enhancing overall system efficiency and performance. Furthermore, three of five switches within proposed architecture operate in any mode with minimal conduction losses, while the remaining two switches function at line frequency, exhibiting negligible switching losses. To regulate proposed inverter topology, a basic pulse width modulation (PWM) using a sine-triangle technique is introduced and rigorously analyzed under all operating conditions. Simulation studies are conducted using MATLAB/SIMULINK to validate the performance and effectiveness of the proposed system.

Keywords— PID controller, DC-DC buck-boost converter, DC-AC converter, Arduino microcontroller.

I. INTRODUCTION

Leakage currents are a common issue in transformer-less inverters powered by photovoltaic (PV) systems. In an effort to lessen the effects of leakage currents, researchers have created a variety of transformer-less inverter topologies and control algorithms, especially for PV-fed systems. The application of a string or grid-tied central inverter serves as an example of this idea. Designs PV panel strings, thereby obviating the requirement for an illustration of this concept is the use of grid-tied central or string inverters. Nature of the PV source necessitates a voltage-boosting step, which, in turn, compromises the overall system efficiency. Numerous studies have produced inverters that may not function when the PV source is low voltage or in shadowed situations are recommended. Given this, it seems that academics are becoming more interested in buck-current advancements in transformer-less topologies that led to the development of boost-based configuration.

The authors proposed a transformer-less inverter design derived from buck-boost principles, which demonstrates effective performance across a broad spectrum of photovoltaic (PV) system applications. Nonetheless, a significant limitation is its requirement for two distinct. Furthermore, an alternative architecture based on buck-boost is introduced, which necessitates only two input inductors and four power switches. In this design, each during either the positive or negative half-cycle, thereby enhancing efficiency. Could result in the injection of DC current. Despite having a single input inductor, this architecture needs a sizable input capacitor to track the PV source's maximum power. The poor voltage gain of this design is another drawback. Topology is suitable for a variety of PV systems. However, power switches. Greater switch counts result in lower system dependability and efficiency as well as greater system costs. For this architecture to track the solar PV maximum point, a greater input capacitance is necessary. The topology is also compatible with a variety of photovoltaic (PV) systems. Every switching cycle, in this architecture involves three switches conducting, which raises conduction losses. This system's requirement for a big, high-capacity inductor at the input diminishes efficiency and increases system size and expense. This is another drawback of the design. Researchers suggested a buck-boost architecture with just two power switches further reduce the number of switches. However, output voltage's positive and negative half-cycles are not symmetrically operated in this design. The voltage present at the input of the photovoltaic (PV) system must exceed the necessary output voltage, which is another drawback of this design. A different topology was suggested with connected inductor. Although this design can yield a high voltage gain at the output, it also conducts three power switches in a single switching cycle, increasing conduction losses and decreasing system efficiency. This proposes a transformer-less inverter topology with a buck-boost design that uses just the following are suggested topology's main benefits. There is no leakage current because grid neutral and PV share a similar terminal. There is a negligible injection of DC current. The system is more dependable and extremely efficient because there are fewer programmable switches. 4. The availability of buck-boost operation allows for a broad range of PV power tracking.

II. PROPOSED TRANSFORMERLESS INVERTER

The structure of proposed inverters provided below:

Fig.1. Block Diagram of Proposed Inverter

A suggested Buck-Boost topology diagram is shown below. The Transformer-less Inverter (BBTI) concept combines a full-bridge inverter with a buck-boost DC-DC converter. This design has five programmable elements. The switches (S1 to S5), an auxiliary capacitor (CA), a power diode (D), and an input inductor (L) are the essential components of the BBTI. The switches S1, S3, S4, and S5 which are among the five switches that run at a high frequency, or switching frequency, are crucial to the system's functionality. S5 and S2, however, are designed to operate intended at a line frequency of 50 Hz. As can be observed, because the PV's negative terminal is connected directly, the BBTI architecture completely prohibits leakage currents.

Fig.2. Circuit Diagram of Proposed system

Current advancements in transformer-less topologies have led to the development of boost-based configurations. The authors proposed a transformer-less inverter design derived from buck-boost principles, which demonstrates effective performance across a broad spectrum of photovoltaic (PV) system applications. Nonetheless, a significant limitation regarding this particular topology is its requirement for two distinct. Furthermore, an alternative transformer-less architecture based on buck-boost is introduced, which necessitates input power switches. In this design, during either positive or negative half-cycle, thereby enhancing efficiency. The several states of switching that align with every mode of operation are shown below:

Table:-1

Operation of BBTI		Switches states (1=ON, 0=OFF)					Mode	
		S ₁	S ₂	S ₃	S ₄	S ₅		D
+Ve half cycle	i _t >0	1	0	1	0	1	0	a
		0	0	0	0	1	1	b
-Ve half cycle		1	1	0	1	0	0	c
		0	1	0	0	0	1	d

The explanations below refer to the four fundamental operational modes of the BBTI, including Mode-(a), where in the BBTI produces electricity for grid. In this configuration, power switches S1, S3, and S5 are engaged. Inductor utilized for energy simultaneously, the energy storage inductor accumulates all active conduction paths associated with operational mode emphasized bold lines as seen below: Storage (L) captures and retains energy sourced from the photovoltaic (PV) system using power switches S1 and S5, while switches S3 and S5, enable auxiliary capacitor CA to supply energy to the grid. As seen below, thick lines indicate all pathways of current flow that align with this mode of operation.

Fig.3. Mode A of Proposed system

Mode-(b): In this specific mode of operation, only switch S5 is engaged, leaving all other switches deactivated. Inductor (L) releases its stored energy through diode 'D', while connected to switch S2, which redirects power into the auxiliary capacitor CA. Meanwhile, switch S5 enables the grid inductor 'Lg' to conduct its current without restriction and S2's anti-parallel diode. The conducting channels that relate to this mode of functioning are underlined with bold lines.

Fig.4. Mode B of Proposed system

Mode-(c): This mode operates during the adverse half-cycle of the grid, power switches S1, S2, and S4 are engaged. In this mode, auxiliary capacitor CA delivers power.

Fig.5. Mode C of Proposed system

Mode-(d): Represents the freewheeling phase of the inductor Lg, which occurs when the power switch remains activated while the other switches are deactivated. In this phase, it transfers its accumulated and antiparallel diode associated with S2. The current flowing through inductor Lg is allowed to pass unobstructed via switch S2 and the antiparallel diode of switch S5, resulting in components conducting channels.

Fig.6. Mode D of Proposed system

The modulation strategy proposed for buck-boost transformer-less inverter (BBTI) topology is illustrated in Figure 3. In this approach, modulation of the system is emphasized as a signal ($V_m \sin(\omega t)$), along with its absolute value ($|V_m \sin(\omega t)|$).

Fig.7. PWM Circuit of Proposed System

The generation of switching pulse for S3 occurs through comparison of $V_m \sin(\omega t)$ with a triangular waveform designated as V_{tr} .

III. THE PROPOSED CONVERTER'S SIMULATION SETTING ARE

Table:2

Parameter/Components	Ratings
Frequency	50Hz
Input voltage	75V
Load resistance	24 Ω
Power rating	300W
Inductor	0.115mH
Switching frequency	10KHz
Capacitor	500μF
IGBT/Switches	Ron=0.001Ω
Output voltage	230V

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

The simulation circuit is provided below:

Fig.8. Simulation circuit

In this, the PV source of 75V, 320W, is providing supply to the inverter, which boosts voltage. Up to 230V and inject power to the grid. The PV voltage, current, and power are provided below:

Fig.9. PV Voltage

The PV voltage is around 75V, and current is 4.5A, and the PV power is around 340W. The inductor current and boosted capacitor voltage are provided below:

Fig.10. Boosted Capacitor Voltage

The capacitor voltage is around 270V and inductor peak current is around 40A

Fig.11. Load Voltage 270V

The load voltage is around 230V and current is around 2A. The load power is provided below:

Fig.12. Load Voltage 230V.The load power is around 300V.

Fig.13. Load Voltage 300V

The efficiency is around 87.5%. The %THD of the proposed inverter is provided below:

Fig.14. Proposed Inverter

The %THD of the proposed inverter is around 1.14%.

V. CONCLUSION

In case of simulation by using MATLAB/SIMULINK software, we have simulated with PWM controller, the operation principles of the proposed converter are studied in PID controller, and the advantages are investigated. With capacitance of coupling capacitor $500\mu\text{F}$, Inductor 0.115mH , to achieve some acceptable efficiency. An entirely new transformer-less buck-boost converter inverter topology has been presented, examined in detail, and supported by experimental results. The ability of the BBTI configuration to inject the leakage current of 0% has been shown. Little DC electricity into the grid, which qualifies it for grid-tied PV (photovoltaic) uses. A broad voltage range can be used to monitor the PV system's maximum power point by employing BBTI's buck-boost capabilities.

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